

ANALYSIS OF A WORK OF ART AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE

Ruhillo Cho‘liyev

Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Philology

Annotation: This article discusses the role of the analysis of the language of a work of art in world linguistics, a brief review of the work carried out in this area in our country, and the significance of studying the composition of a literary text.

Keywords: linguistics, literary text, statistics, etymology, lexical units, linguoculturology

As world science changes and develops in socio-economic, political, and other aspects, these changes are reflected, first of all, in the lexicon of each language.

In world linguistics, it is always an urgent issue to study and study the lexicon of any period, to analyze the changes that have occurred and are occurring in it, to study the language of literary works, to analyze the statistics of lexical units, to give a historical-etymological, thematic-semantic classification, to reveal their stylistic features. The extent to which this is urgent can be explained by the following factors:

- the language, first of all, reflects the historical ethnogenesis of each nation, which in turn reflects the historical-psychological image of this nation. With the development of the language, it is possible to determine the foundations of the civilization of the nation. Bertels: “Language is the soul of the nation”, Abdulla Avloni: “The eternal life of each nation, which is its existence in the world, is its language and literature”, - one can see that their thoughts are right.

-A work of art is a unique field where the folk language can fully demonstrate all its rich possibilities, and these possibilities can be fully utilized depending on the level of skill of the creator. These possibilities are limitless, and studying the issue of their realization in a particular work is the basis for demonstrating, first of all, the writer’s skill in the artistic language, and, secondly, the richness of the means of expression in the folk language.

-Creating ideographic, lexicographic and other dictionaries based on literary works from the point of view of language possibilities. This will also help us study the ideology of the people and contribute to the development of lexicography.

In the thousand-year history of our literature, there are many literary works that objectively embody such boundless possibilities of our language. However, during the authoritarian regime, it was not allowed to study the works of such great poets of the nation as Abdulla Qodiriy, Cholpon, Fitrat. In the early years of Uzbekistan’s

independence, the first President of our Republic, I. A. Karimov, said: "...The names of prominent people who were deliberately erased from the memory of our people during the era of authoritarianism are being restored one by one. The spiritual heritage of dozens of figures who died for the freedom of our homeland and nation, such as Abdulla Qodiri, Abdulhamid Cholpon, Abdurauf Fitrat and Usman Nasir, is returning to the memory of our people today".

The events taking place in the world geopolitical arena and the fact that peoples are undergoing a process of sharp integration are causing a fundamental change in their national thinking. During the time when Abdulla Qodiri lived, the same flow of processes threatened our country. The depiction of such social and political changes is not clearly reflected in Abdulla Qodiri's novels, but the impact of socio-economic and political processes is clearly felt in his small prose works. This, of course, cannot but affect the lexical composition and semantic characteristics of the language of that nation. Considering this, the study of lexical layers of meaning and stylistic aspects of lexical units of any period, the study of linguistic statistics of the vocabulary in literary texts, and the study of the form and meaning characteristics of units in speech structures show that the topic is very relevant. Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in his holiday greetings to the people on the occasion of the Uzbek language holiday, said: "It is known that in the study and development of any language, first of all, its theoretical and methodological foundations play a major role. From this point of view, the publication of more than 40 fundamental books in recent years, such as "Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", "Alisher Navoi Encyclopedia", "Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur Encyclopedia", "Philosophy Encyclopedia", "Legal Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", "Encyclopedia of Islam", "Spirituality: Dictionary of Basic Concepts", "Pedagogy: Encyclopedia", "Dictionary of Historical Terms", "Dictionary of Literary Studies", "Dictionary of Legal Terms", was an important step on this path.

Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-4797 dated May 13, 2016 "On the establishment of the Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi", No. PF-5850 dated October 21, 2019 "On measures to radically increase the prestige and status of the Uzbek language as the state language", No. PF-6084 dated October 20, 2020 "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language and improve language policy in our country", No. PF-6097 dated October 29, 2020 "On the Concept for the Development of Science until 2030"; It serves to a certain extent in the practical implementation of the tasks set out in the resolutions of the Academy of Sciences No. PQ-2789 dated February 17, 2017 "On measures to further improve the activities of the Academy of Sciences, the organization, management and financing of scientific research work", No. PQ-2909

dated April 20, 2017 “On measures to further develop the higher education system”, No. PQ-3271 dated September 13, 2017 “On the program of comprehensive measures to develop the system of publishing and distributing book products, increase and promote book reading and reading culture”, and other regulatory and legal documents related to this activity.

In Uzbek linguistics, problems of the artistic language, in particular, the works of several writers, have been subjected to lexical-semantic and stylistic analysis.

But Abdulla Qodiriy’s short prose works have been studied very little. Linguistic statistical analysis of the short prose works of such a great word artist as Abdulla Qodiriy, who created a unique school of examples in the field of literary language, highlighting the semantic properties of words, and determining their relationship with the current Uzbek literary language is an extremely urgent task. Academic writer Oybek noted in his work “The Creative Path of Abdulla Qodiriy”: “In the novel “Otgan kunlar” the writer showed great mastery over the language. The language of the novel is truly rich, colorful, simple, with great expressive power, and understandable to the public. The role of this work in the formation of the Uzbek literary language is undoubtedly enormous”.

It is very important to study and analyze polysemy, metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, simile and irony, synonym, antonym, stable combinations, archaism, historicism, neologisms, words of personal creation, common and limited words, which increase the value of a work of art and are the object of study in the field of linguistics.

Taking these into account, the study of lexical semantic, functional-semantic properties of words belonging to the own and assimilated layer, limited and common, historical and obsolete compounds, onomastic units, types of words according to their form and meaning, lexical semantic, functional-semantic properties of lexical units can provide practical assistance in imagining and thinking about the linguistic and cultural image of humanity in different periods.

List of references:

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